

FLEX Innovation Platform (FLIP): Mission Overview. Manny Shar¹, Luke Walker², Kelly Randell³, ¹Astrolab, manny.shar@astrolab.space, ²Astrolab Luke.walker@astrolab.space, ³Astrolab, kelly.randell@astrolab.space..

Introduction: The FLEX Innovation Platform (FLIP) is a unique mission to the Mons Mouton region of the lunar south pole scheduled to launch in mid-2026. Astrolab conceived of the mission in response to the VIPER cancellation in 2024 and has designed, built, and is undergoing flight qualification testing in under 20 months. FLIP will be the largest American rover on the moon since the Apollo Lunar Rover Vehicles. FLIP will serve several critical functions for the future of lunar south pole exploration: 1) science investigations for lunar environments investigations, 2) technology maturation of key technologies for future lunar rovers including NASA’s Lunar Terrain Vehicle (LTV), and 3) characterizing performance of mobility, perception, and thermal systems in the challenging lunar south pole environment. In the process, Astrolab is gaining valuable corporate experience in designing, building, qualifying, and operating a lunar mobility vehicle.

We provide a mission overview on the FLIP mission, including current vehicle build and test status, the payloads and science investigations on FLIP, and our future plans.

Figure 1 FLIP terrestrial egress testing and render of FLIP driving away from the Astrobotic Griffin lander

Vehicle Build and Test: The FLIP rover is a unique design informed by the constraints in its conception and purpose as a technology development platform. NASA cancelled VIPER in 2024 due to cost increases, launch delays, and risks of future cost growth [1], but maintained the Astrobotic Griffin Lander as a part of the Commercial Lunar Payload Services (CLPS) program. Astrolab contracted with Astrobotic for the available space on Griffin and began designing a vehicle.

FLIP is a four-wheeled skid steer rover limited to the geometry and launch mass (480kg) initially designed for VIPER. FLIP includes mobility components designed and sized for the larger FLEX vehicle, including innovative warm-blooded flexible tires from Astrolab’s strategic partner Venturi Space and high-power wheel actuators. The remaining systems were selected for applicability to future vehicles and ability to procure within the limited timeframe of development.

The vehicle is currently going through protoqualification and the start of the TVAC campaign before being shipped to Cape Canaveral for launch on a Falcon Heavy.

Figure 2 The FLIP rover in integration at Astrolab.

Payloads and Science Investigations: FLIP hosts in excess of 15 payloads, including science instruments associated with four separate NASA centers, as well as commercial and outreach opportunities. FLIP will carry out important investigations for dust, perception, lunar environments, and regolith composition.

Operational Concept: As a mission of opportunity, Astrolab is developing FLIP’s operational concept for flexibility in landing times, communications availability, and lunar hibernation. Payload operations and science investigations will be integrated with lunar traverses.

References:

- [1] NASA, 2024, “NASA Ends VIPER Project, Continues Moon Exploration”, <https://www.nasa.gov/news-release/nasa-ends-viper-project-continues-moon-exploration/>